

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF GENDER ON LABORATORY PARAMETERS AND LENGTH OF HOSPITAL STAY IN HOSPITALIZED COVID-19 PATIENTS: A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT. The aim of this study is to retrospectively compare the demographic data, biochemical parameters, and length of hospital stay of patients hospitalized due to COVID-19 according to gender, and to determine the effect of gender on the COVID-19. A total of 191 COVID-19 patients who were hospitalized and treated in the hospital were included in the study. Statistical analyses of the data were performed using Jamovi V. 1.8.1 software. The distribution of the data was checked for homogeneity with the Levene test, and the WBC and day parameters were tested using the Mann Whitney-U test, while other parameters were tested with t-test in independent variables. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. According to the results of our study, the average age of male patients was found to be 64.58 ± 14.52 , while the average age of female patients was found to be 70.72 ± 12.74 . Statistically significant differences were found between male and female COVID-19 patients in terms of hemoglobin, monocyte count, and length of hospital stay, except for the age parameter. No differences were found in other biochemical or inflammatory parameters examined, such as D-dimer, AST, ALT, or CRP. In female patients, hemoglobin levels, monocyte levels, and length of hospital stay were lower compared to males. The average length of hospital stay was 7.55 days in males and 7.45 days in females. Our retrospective analysis revealed that gender differences have an impact on COVID-19. We believe it is necessary to further explore the impact of gender on COVID-19 infection to better understand how to address this public health issue.

Keywords: *COVID-19, gender, length of stay, SARS-CoV-2.*

INTRODUCTION

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) was identified as the cause of the severe acute respiratory syndrome epidemic in Wuhan City, China in

December 2019, and the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has since killed more than 6.5 million people worldwide causing a major pandemic worldwide [1]. The COVID-19 epidemic due to SARS-CoV-2 is still ongoing, and the infection can cause very different symptoms and it has been seen that it can affect different tissues, including the liver, kidney and cardiovascular system, as well as the respiratory system [2].

Epidemiological data have consistently shown that since the beginning of the epidemic, both the severity of the infection and the mortality rate have been higher in men than in women [3]. Patients with comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension and cardiovascular diseases are at higher risk of severe COVID-19 infection. It is known that men are similarly more likely to show such comorbidities than women [4].

Hormonal differences between the sexes affect both our response to stress and inflammatory processes. SARS-CoV-2 binding or replication is likely affected at the molecular level due to both genetic and hormonal differences. In addition, specific genes associated with the immune system such as TLR4, TLR7 and TLR8 are located on the X chromosome [5]. In a study conducted on approximately 15000 women in Sweden, it was shown that women who took estrogen hormone replacement therapy had approximately 50% less risk of COVID-19 than women who did not take it, and showed that it had a significant effect especially on estrogen [6]. Therefore, in our study, we aimed to compare the biochemical parameters and hospitalization times of hospitalized COVID-19 patients in terms of gender.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This research was conducted at Medipol University, non-interventional clinical research By the Ethics Committee (dated 19.09.2023 and 117 number) approved. In this retrospective study, 191 laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 patients, aged 18 years and older, who were admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) at Ankara 29 Mayıs State Hospital between May 14, 2021, and March 21, 2022, were analyzed. COVID-19 diagnosis was confirmed through reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) testing of nasopharyngeal swab samples. SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia was diagnosed based on WHO guidelines. Patients requiring respiratory support or exhibiting oxygen saturation levels below 90% with a standard oxygen mask were admitted to the ICU. Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) was diagnosed according to the Berlin definition [7].

Data were collected from electronic medical records and patient files by researchers at the Intensive Care Department of Ankara 29 Mayıs State Hospital. Given the retrospective nature of the study, individual written informed consent was not obtained.

Demographic and clinical data collected included age, disease severity at ICU admission, gender, time from symptom onset to ICU admission and intubation, and scores from the Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE II) and the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA). Underlying comorbidities, such as chronic cardiac and lung diseases, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, chronic liver and renal failure, malignancies, autoimmune disorders, cerebrovascular diseases, and immunosuppressive conditions, were also documented.

Patients were compared based on gender, age, length of ICU stay, and key blood parameters. Statistical analyses were performed using Jamovi software (Version 1.8.1). Data distribution was assessed, and homogeneity was evaluated using Levene's test. The

Mann-Whitney U test was applied to compare white blood cell (WBC) counts and ICU stay duration, while other parameters were analyzed using t-tests for independent variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 191 hospitalized COVID-19 patients were included in the study. Of the COVID-19 patients included in the study, 81 (42.41%) were female and 110 (57.59%) were male. While the mean age of the male patients was 64.58 ± 14.52 , the mean age of the female patients was 70.72 ± 12.74 ($p < 0.05$). A statistically significant difference was found between female and male COVID-19 patients in terms of hemoglobin, monocytes amount and number of hospitalization days, except for age parameter ($p < 0.05$). No difference was found in other biochemical parameters such as Ddimer, AST, ALT or inflammatory parameters such as CRP ($p > 0.05$). Hemoglobin levels, monocyte levels and hospitalization times were found to be lower in female patients compared to males. The mean hospital stay was found to be 7.55 days in men and 7.45 days in women (Table 1). The distribution of hospital stay by gender is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution of hospital stays of COVID-19 patients by gender.

Due to the roles of sex hormones and sex chromosomes on both immune cells and regulatory genes, gender-based differences are detected in the inflammatory process, and the risk of COVID-19 disease is higher in men than in women, which is attributed to these reasons [1].

According to the data obtained from studies conducted around the world, in individuals catching COVID 19; It has been found that the risk of death is higher in men compared to women (9). In addition, according to WHO data, according to the data obtained in COVID 19 patients among 55 countries, it has been understood that men are affected by this disease compared to women in 48 countries and that more deaths occur in men [10-13]. In these case-death rates, the first factor is considered to be age, and the second factor

is gender. In addition to these potential differences based on gender, gender, social role, acquired identity and social relations are also a reason for the difference in the COVID-19's vulnerability between genders [14-17]. The first public health measure taken in the COVID-19 pandemic was fundamental changes in individual behaviors such as social distancing and wearing masks [16,17]. High-risk behaviors, including smoking and alcohol, seem to be more common in men in general in many societies. The fact that men work in high-risk jobs such as using public transport is higher than women, which is thought to be a reason why men are more likely to catch the disease [13-16]

It is estimated that sex-linked hormones are effective in the prognosis of the disease. It is known that the immunity of women is stronger than men for many infectious diseases, not only for COVID-19 disease [8,9,18,19,25]. It is known that hormones according to gender differences are effective on the severity and results of COVID-19 infections. Estrogen in women promotes both innate and adaptive immune responses, causing faster clearance of pathogens, less severe symptoms in women, and a stronger immune response to vaccines [26-28]. The strong immune system that women have, high interferon and antibody production against pathogens is caused by the estrogen hormone, and this strong immunity decreases with age during menopause [29]. Estrogen has an anti-inflammatory effect by modulating the immune system. Most of the cytokines, namely IL-6, IL-8 and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) are known to be inhibited by periovulatory doses of estrogen. This is why postmenopausal women have high levels of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-1, IL-6 and TNF- α due to low estrogen levels. In addition, it has been observed that immunity is increased in HIV patients receiving high levels of estrogen, the survival rate after influenza infection is increased in mice supplemented with high estrogen, and the cytokine level in their lungs is low [30-31].

Since COVID-19 is a systemic infection, it can cause various inflammatory responses, cellular and biochemical changes in individuals [32]. Although the symptoms seen in COVID-19 patients and the affected areas and organs differ in each patient; It is known to cause changes in gastrointestinal system organs [32,33], liver [34], kidneys [35] and heart [36]. As a result of the damage to these vital organs, blood parameters also vary drastically. When the biochemical parameters are examined, it has been determined that biochemical parameters such as bilirubin, urea, creatinine, myoglobin and coagulation factors differ according to gender in terms of COVID-19. In addition, it is known that the morbidity rate in patients with COVID-19 foot is different according to gender, and the death rate is higher in men [37]. The reason for gender inequality seen in COVID-19 patients; biological differences, gender-specific behavioral factors and pre-existing comorbidity rates are thought to be the cause [38, 39]. Therefore, it is normal to observe gender and age differences in the results of laboratory analyzes. In a large-scale study conducted in Brazil, a total of more than 4.5 million records of 434 laboratory parameters were compared for 39,391 men and women with COVID-19 of different age groups. As a result of this study, it was revealed that several blood parameter combinations can be markers in the evaluation of disease severity. In this study by Ten-Caten et al., patients were divided into three age groups. No significant difference was found in the blood parameters of the patients in the 0-12 age group.

Some gender-related changes in laboratory parameters of COVID-19 patients aged 13-60 were detected, as in our study. Although no difference was detected in other biochemical parameters such as Ddimer, AST, ALT, or in inflammatory parameters such as CRP in our study, hemoglobin amount, monocyte level and hospitalization time were found to be lower in female patients compared to males. Ten-Caten et al., in their study,

determined differences in gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), C-reactive protein (CRP) and ferritin values. As in our study, it was determined that male patients stayed longer in the intensive care unit, and the number of male patients in the intensive care unit was found to be higher than the number of female patients [37-40].

Laccarino et al. reported that male gender is a determining factor for ICU admissions in COVID-19 patients. In addition, gender-specific analyzes revealed that obesity, chronic kidney disease, and hypertension had higher rates of intensive care admission among men. Previous studies worldwide have associated obesity and heart failure with higher ICU admission rates among women [22,41].

Ten-Caten et al. observed coagulopathy in 50.4% of male patients hospitalized in the intensive care unit with COVID-19. The increase in blood levels of markers such as CRP, ferritin, and fibrinogen causes an increase in proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, which creates the inflammatory response in COVID-19 patients [38,41]. These changes were most commonly observed in older men. Although the amount of hemoglobin and monocytes in our study was found to be lower in women than in men, in the study of Ten-Caten et al., complete blood count parameters were found to be at low levels in both men and women. The reason for this may be external factors such as starting habits, habits and genetic factors [38,39,41].

Thrombocytopenia is thought to be an early indicator of the disease due to the decrease in platelet counts in COVID-19 patients [42,43,44]. Although lymphopenia is considered a symptom of COVID-19 disease, it was determined in our study that the decrease in lymphocyte cell count was moderate. Similarly, Ten-Caten et al. did not detect a significant decrease in lymphocyte count in patients with COVID-19. It is known that eosinophils activate CD8+ T cells during viral infection such as COVID-19 and female sex hormones regulate eosinophilia [45,46,47,48,49]. Li et al. reported that 989 patients with COVID-19 had eosinopenia and elevated CRP. Very high CRP values were not found in our study [47].

Addressing gender-related differences and disparities in COVID-19 infection rates and outcomes is essential for improving public health responses and healthcare systems. Future research should prioritize these issues, particularly in community settings, to generate evidence-based recommendations that can help reduce gender-related gaps in healthcare access, treatment, and outcomes [50,51]. Such insights will be critical in tailoring interventions that are sensitive to the specific needs of different gender groups and in promoting equity in healthcare delivery. Furthermore, ongoing and future randomized controlled trials investigating gender-specific differences in COVID-19 should ensure balanced and adequate representation of both sexes. This is crucial for producing generalizable findings that accurately reflect the experiences and responses of diverse populations. Without this representation, the unique biological and social factors influencing disease susceptibility, progression, and recovery in different genders may be overlooked. These observational and randomized studies underscore the importance of understanding how sex and gender influence various aspects of COVID-19, from infection rates to immune responses and long-term health outcomes. By integrating gender-sensitive analyses into COVID-19 research, we can better identify specific risk factors, optimize treatment protocols, and improve overall health outcomes for all individuals, irrespective of gender. This approach not only addresses existing disparities but also strengthens the overall response to current and future public health crises.

Table 1. Distribution of demographic data, biochemical parameters and length of stay data of hospitalized COVID-19 patients.

Parameter (Unit)	Gender	N	Median	Median	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	p
AGE (year)	Woman	81	70.728	71.000	12.747	14.163	0.003*
	Man	110	64.582	65.000	14.524	13.848	
HEMOGLOBIN	Woman	81	11.307	11.400	1.938	0.2153	0.001*
	Man	110	12.921	13.000	2.122	0.2033	
WBC	Woman	81	13.886	10.270	19.895	22.106	0.52
	Man	110	11.004	9.790	5.752	0.5510	
NEUTROPHIL	Woman	81	84.965	88.100	12.204	13.560	0.14
	Man	110	81.896	85.200	15.435	14.784	
MONOSITE	Woman	81	0.459	0.360	0.348	0.0386	0.03*
	Man	110	0.575	0.490	0.367	0.0351	
LYMPHOCYTE	Woman	81	9.159	7.500	6.696	0.7440	0.36
	Man	110	10.152	7.900	7.878	0.7546	
PLT	Woman	81	282.654	260.000	134.425	149.362	0.06
	Man	110	246.560	233.000	124.761	119.499	
AST	Woman	81	105.344	28.000	364.737	410.361	0.49
	Man	110	74.514	31.000	253.970	245.522	
ALT	Woman	81	97.643	29.000	379.070	426.488	0.51
	Man	110	71.257	36.000	151.653	145.258	
BUN	Woman	81	30.266	21.000	23.394	26.320	0.79
	Man	110	31.295	21.000	27.773	27.103	
CREATINE	Woman	81	1.039	0.670	0.940	0.1058	0.92
	Man	110	1.051	0.820	0.831	0.0796	
AMYLASE	Woman	81	84.754	66.000	87.736	105.622	0.8
	Man	110	88.471	62.000	99.498	106.673	
CRP	Woman	81	61.894	24.805	74.962	83.810	0.13
	Man	110	79.915	53.590	85.734	82.498	
DDİMER	Woman	81	2.927	1.310	5.730	0.6407	0.92
	Man	110	3.005	1.175	5.612	0.5503	
Number of Hospitalization Days (Days)	Woman	81	7.457	7.000	5.310	0.5901	0.05
	Man	110	7.555	5.000	9.267	0.8836	

* p<0.05

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, according to the retrospective analysis we performed in our study, it was determined that gender differences have an impact on COVID-19. We believe it is necessary to further explore the impact of gender on COVID-19 infection to better understand how to address this public health issue. Future studies should focus on identifying the underlying factors that contribute to gender differences in COVID-19, such as biological differences, social determinants of health, and access to healthcare.

Understanding these factors can help inform evidence-based recommendations for decision-making aimed at reducing gender gaps in the healthcare system. It is also important for ongoing research to include adequate representation of both genders in randomized studies to ensure that any gender-specific differences are properly accounted for. Ensuring that research findings are generalizable and healthcare interventions are effective for all individuals, regardless of gender, can help improve overall outcomes. Addressing gender in COVID-19 infection is a crucial step towards creating a more equitable and effective healthcare system.

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Conflict of Interest. The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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